

LEARNING THE FUNDAMENTALS OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to learning a theoretical and scientific approach to demonstrating understanding of the concept of formative assessment, defining the concept, identifying differences, determining the benefits of assessment, and mastering the skills of using assessment tools.*

Keywords: *formative, summative, evaluation, differentiation, understanding, tools, professional skill, knowledge, standard, information, process, goal.*

Introduction

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 PD-134 "On approval of the national program for the development of school education in 2022-2026" and Resolution of the President of April 20, 2023 PR-128 "On measures to accelerate the comprehensive development of the educational system by improving the quality of scientific, methodical and research work" on the basis of training, retraining and advanced forms of training of leaders and pedagogical personnel of educational organizations, creating conditions for continuous improvement of teachers' professional skills and Resolution PR-54 of February 2, 2024 "On additional measures to accelerate reforms in the field of education, the system of training, retraining and upgrading of pedagogical personnel" recorded in the 2nd Project of innovative and integrated approaches in the educational system are gaining importance in order to ensure the performance of the main tasks, such as the tasks of analysis, introduction of differentiated educational programs that match the knowledge and interests of teachers.

Research materials and methodology

In connection with the funding of the "All Children Succeed" project of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), in cooperation with the Ministry of Preschool and School Education, the National Agency for Social Protection, scientific and practical activities are being carried out on the implementation of a type of new assessment - formative assessment processes in the education system of primary grades in Uzbekistan.

The purpose of this type of assessment is to: Demonstrate understanding of the concept of formative assessment; Define the concept of formative assessment; Determine the differences between formative assessment and summative assessment; Identify the benefits of formative assessment; Master the skills of using formative assessment tools. What is formative assessment? There are many ways to assess knowledge, and they all serve an important purpose. We focus on standardized tests that are associated with higher scores in most cases.

Formative assessment is assessment without grading. This is an assessment that helps students identify gaps and problems in their learning. This type of assessment helps the instructional process, and the teacher can think about the following questions: How can I adapt the teaching process to meet the different needs of different students? Elementary school students

take TIMSS, PIRLS, national exams, and end-of-term assessments, among the standardized tests associated with high performance.

Elementary teachers currently use methods such as quizzes, homework, essays, and projects to assess student learning. When we talk about assessment, we often think of formal assessment methods. Parents and students can wait for their grades during the lesson or during the week, and in many cases, students can't fully express their ideas due to fear of making mistakes and nervousness.

Formative assessment is non-grading assessment that helps students identify gaps and problems in their learning. This type of assessment helps the learning process and allows the teacher to think about how to adapt the teaching process to meet the needs of the students.

Research results

Formative assessment is assessment for the purpose of learning (process), summative assessment is assessment of learning (learned knowledge). Formative assessment is carried out continuously during each lesson, and summative assessment is carried out at the end of the section, quarter, academic year. Formative assessment is not graded, while summative assessment is graded. Formative assessment provides feedback to improve learning and teaching, while summative assessment measures and evaluates learning outcomes. The purpose of formative assessment is to monitor the learning process, while the purpose of summative assessment is to assess knowledge.

Formative assessment - Purpose: To improve the learning process. Monitors the student's progress. Time - Duration - is carried out in each lesson. Type of assessment - Inferior, informal and non-standardized, not graded. Expected result - Providing feedback on improving the learning process.

Summative assessment - Purpose: To assess the level of student learning. Time - At the end of an educational process or at the end of an academic year. Type of assessment - Higher, more formal and standardized assessment. Expected Outcome - Grades or scores used to measure mastery. Tasks for formative and summative assessment may be the same. It is carried out in cooperation with educational activities related to formative assessment.

New methodological approaches of modern textbooks: 5E model. In the lesson: you will learn about the essence and stages of the 5E model aimed at developing students' interest in learning, intellectual and creative abilities and creating a positive learning environment; you will learn to apply the 5E model in lessons.

Stage 1. Attracting attention - At this stage, it is necessary to activate the basic knowledge of students, to attract their attention to the topic, to interest them in learning a new topic, to encourage them to pay attention to the studied object, scientific phenomenon or problem. In order to implement this step, the teacher can show a picture, table, graph, model, etc., which encourages students to ask questions about what kind of life experience, imagination and concepts they have about the topic. An important part of this stage is to determine the basic knowledge of students. The result of the 1st stage: the students' basic knowledge is determined, their interest in learning the subject increases.

Stage 2. Research - This stage requires searching for answers to questions. This is done in the form of working with various sources of information or observing, experimenting. The teacher offers students to learn scientific research methods and scientific concepts related to the topic through a practical task. Students work in groups and ask research questions.

Stage 3. Explanation - The teacher asks the students to explain what they have learned and observed in the previous steps. The teacher can explain the content of scientific concepts in more detail. In order for students to better master scientific concepts, it is advisable to use not only verbal, but also video and audio materials in the lesson. The teacher should not be alarmed if the students cannot immediately apply the knowledge acquired in the previous stages at this stage, because the acquisition of scientific concepts takes time.

Step 4. Application - Students apply the knowledge and skills acquired in the research and explanation phases to an unfamiliar situation. It is desirable to ensure interdisciplinary integration at this stage. Studying the natural sciences in relation to mathematics, art, technology and other subjects allows for better mastery of scientific concepts. Outcome of stage 4: students acquire better scientific concepts and skills.

Step 5. Assessment - Assessment serves to determine the level of knowledge and skill acquisition by students. Assessment aims to gather evidence of the extent to which learning outcomes have been achieved. Formative assessment is an assessment for learning and serves to ensure consistent and systematic learning of learning material by students. Formative assessment, by its essence, is a reflexive assessment that uses a mechanism of constant feedback between subjects of the educational process. Summative evaluation is carried out to determine the level of achievement of educational goals after the completion of studies, with points assigned for a specific academic period (quarter, year), as well as for topics, chapters, sections of the curriculum.

Assessment includes determining the level of students' acquisition of theoretical and practical knowledge. Assessment is aimed at gathering evidence of the extent to which learning outcomes have been achieved. The result of step 5: the teacher determines the mastery level of each student and class. Formative assessment can be done in the form of observation or a short question and answer. In the summative assessment, closed tests with multiple answers or open-answer tests are used.

Discussions

Directions for the Puzzle Strategy: Each table group is responsible for one formative assessment topic. You play the role of an expert on the subject and teach the information to other participants. Study the information on the topic and identify the main points. Be prepared to share information with others. Reflection: What are the advantages of "Pazl" (Jigsaw)? How can this strategy be used in the classroom? What type of formative assessment is being implemented?

Feedback: Mind Map - Directions: Open the notebooks, draw a circle in the middle and write formative assessment inside it. Have them draw different small lines from the center and draw shapes to add to their formative assessment notes. Tip: Your notes may be the same as the main topics of today's sessions. Reflection: Exercise "3, 2, 1". Exit Tickets - Instructions: Write the answers to the questions on a piece of paper. Submit your exit ticket before you leave. Questions: 3 things I learned. 2 things I liked or found interesting about the workshop today. I have 1 question. Tip: You can review the mind map if there is a topic that is unclear to you, or if you need more information.

Directions for completing the "Agree/Disagree" exercise: This chart contains a series of statements. I would ask you to think about each affirmation and decide what you think about it. Do you agree with this statement? Do you totally agree? Disagree? Totally disagree? Not sure whether to join or not? Facilitator: "The table contains a number of confirmations. Think about each statement, decide what you think about it, and complete the chart. So, do you agree with this

statement? Do you totally agree? Or do you disagree? Totally disagree? Thinking about joining or not? (Are you neutral?)". The process of performing the exercise: a. Listeners are asked to answer the statements in the table individually. b. Confirmations are displayed on the screen. Each affirmation is read aloud to allow time for the audience to respond. c. Listeners are asked to share their answers with the group. If the participants want, the discussion can be done in pairs. During the discussion, participants should share their answers and explain why they gave that answer. d. The facilitator moves around the room to make sure the audience understands the task and to help when needed. e. Questions are asked to develop students' thinking skills about group work.

A *T-Chart* can be learned through a graphic organizer that helps organize data: A T-Chart is a useful tool for comparing and contrasting. In addition, here is a guide to using the T-Chart of student understanding: Create a T-Chart with formative assessment on the left and summative assessment on the right. Use the internet to learn more about the difference between formative and summative assessment. Write the differences you find using the T-chart. Give examples of each type of assessment.

Benefits of Formative Assessment - How does formative assessment affect teachers, students, and the learning environment? Directions: Each table will develop a poster about the benefits of formative assessment. You can create a poster with any look you like. Our sole purpose is to illustrate the benefits of formative assessment - but in any way you want.

Reflection: Research has shown that student learning outcomes improve when teachers use formative assessment in their lessons. Directions: Fill in the blanks to complete the sentence.

Formative assessment is ____.

Formative assessment is not ____.

Formative assessment differs from summative assessment because ____.

Exercise ____ is an example of formative assessment.

The benefits of formative assessment are ____.

Universal Design in Education: Lesson Objective: Recognizes that all children learn differently and have different needs in expressing their knowledge. Describes how TUD promotes inclusive education practices in teaching and learning environments. "Let's think together!" ("Think-Pair-Share") — "How do you learn?" How did they get you to learn? The term universal design in education is derived from the concept of universal design, which means that the principle of design is to create a comfortable environment for everyone.

Universal design is planning the design of structures from the ground up to make them better, cheaper and more usable. So, what does this mean in the classroom? Pay attention to our classes. How can teachers create a barrier-free classroom environment for all students? TUD means that we are required to provide students with multiple ways to engage and learn. We also need to allow students to present their new knowledge in ways that work best for them. Universal design in education is based on these three key principles: engagement, presentation, and multiple means of action and expression.

Information about student 1: Sevara

Sevara studies in the first grade. At the age of five, a cochlear implant was installed in her. Her hearing and speech have improved, but she sometimes struggles to understand verbal instructions on one try. Although Sevara's pronunciation is slowly improving, she still hesitates to speak in front of her classmates.

UDE for the class	
School area	Different means of attraction (how are students engaged and motivated?)
Various means of presenting information (how do students learn new information?)	Different means of movement and expression (how do students express what they have learned?)

A Tour of the Gallery: TUD for the Classroom. Study each group activity for five minutes (we'll tell you when to switch places). Read the student information and plan given to the group. Write your question on the yellow sticker. Write any additional strategies you suggest on a sticky note.

Reflection - Which of the TUD strategies you used would benefit the class? What challenges have you faced in meeting the needs of students? What factors (staff, assistive devices, teaching and learning materials, etc.) help you meet the needs of all learners? Name one TUD strategy you've seen in another group and want to try. Do you have other ideas?

Conclusion

Vygotsky's "Zone of Proximal Development" theory: The zone of proximal development is the gap between what a child can do independently and what he cannot do at all. In this, he learns to solve the problem with the help of a teacher or a peer who has more knowledge. It tells where students learn.

Scaffolding and Collaborative Learning: By providing scaffolding or graded support, teachers can help students achieve things they would not be able to do on their own. Although you have learned about the "zone of proximal development" when considering a non-inclusive classroom, it is also extremely important in implementing inclusive education. We want to challenge all students to do things beyond what they can already do on their own, while providing them with a scaffolding method for success. In this way, we support their learning.

In the inclusive classroom, the ZPD theory fits well with the cooperative learning strategy. Students can solve problems in small groups, in groups of different levels, including students with disabilities. By working together, children can support each other and achieve more than they are capable of. Advanced learners deepen their understanding by explaining or teaching concepts, and less advanced learners strive to do more with the guidance of their peers than they can do alone.

Organize a group discussion:

- student-student cooperation;
- parent-student cooperation;
- brother and sister partnership;
- cooperation between teacher and students.

Facilitators: Facilitators are strategies that help students learn the same curriculum or content as their peers. The expected results and goals of education remain the same. Facilitators can modify the environment, curriculum format, or tools to help students understand content and/or complete a task. Some ways to create conditions include:

- listening to audio recordings instead of reading the text;

reduce the number of tasks on the page;
giving answers orally rather than in writing;
performing tests in a different environment, such as a quieter room with fewer distractions;
giving more time to complete the task.

Student information: What tools can be suggested to use?

Abdulaziz is hard of hearing, he wears a hearing aid. Sometimes, there is a lot of noise in his ears and he has trouble concentrating. Abdulaziz faces difficulties due to his speech defects.

Rashid was diagnosed with DYGS (SDVG). He is very polite and enjoys conversation, but has trouble concentrating on tasks for long periods of time. He has sufficient ability to absorb information at the grade level he is studying.

Gulnara is a 3rd grader and she was diagnosed with autism. Her creative thinking skills are highly developed and she loves science. She faces difficulties in the process of transitioning from one lesson to another or from one exercise to another. At the same time, it is difficult to follow long instructions.

Adaptations: During the adaptation process, changes are made to certain parts of the curriculum to make learning objectives, tasks performed, or content more understandable. During customization, the level of difficulty, content, or learning criteria are changed. Since the results of the lesson are not the same, children with disabilities participate in the lesson meaningfully and effectively.

General Adaptations: Solve simplified math problems on the test; Create an alternative project; Evaluation using a different standard or rubric than peers. In general, adaptation is used when a student cannot learn with the help of the means of creating a comfortable environment.

Where to start? See the standards:

What is the purpose of the lesson?

How do you plan to demonstrate that students have mastered this knowledge?

Think about your student(s):

What are their strengths?

What challenges will they face in this lesson?

What obstacles can I overcome?

What tools do students need to create comfortable conditions?

What adaptations do students need?

Conclusion - our considerations lead us to the following approach:

- Assessment serves to determine the level of knowledge and skills acquisition of students.
- Assessment aims to gather evidence of the extent to which learning outcomes have been achieved.

Formative assessment is an assessment for learning and serves to ensure consistent and systematic learning of learning material by students. Formative assessment, by its essence, is a reflexive assessment that uses a mechanism of constant feedback between subjects of the educational process.

Summative assessment is used to determine the level of achievement of educational goals after the end of the study with a score for a specific academic period (quarter, year), as well as for topics, chapters, sections of the curriculum.

REFERENCES

1. Decree No. PF-134 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 "On approval of the national program for the development of school education in 2022-2026".
2. Decree No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".
3. Guide to the "All Children Succeed" project of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID): - Tashkent. August 2024.
4. www.google.kz